

PHYSICAL EDUCATION AS A MEDIUM TO MENTALLY RETARDED STUDENTS' SELF DEVELOPMENTS

Muhamad Bram Riyadi¹ⁱ,

Sugiyanto²,

M. Furqon Hidayatullah³

^{1,2,3} Department of Sport Science, Post-graduate Program,
Sebelas Maret University, Surakarta 57126, Indonesia

Abstract:

This study aims to (1) Obtain the phenomenon overview of mentally retarded students in everyday life. (2) Determine the motion behaviors of mentally retarded students outside and inside physical education activities. (3) Figure out the mentally retarded students' ability in joining the activities of physical education and any obstacles faced by them. (4) Figure out how teachers give the treatments to mentally retarded students while they are doing sports activities in physical education. (5) Figure out the activities of physical education for students' self-developments. Subject of this research are mentally retarded students at Special Education School with Multiple Disabilities of Bina Sejahtera Surakarta. This study was using qualitative methods Life story-Case Study with four criteria used; the degree of confidence (credibility), transferability, dependability, and certainty (conformability). The degree of confidence was examined by using triangulation of data from the informant who was considered as a person who was close enough to the mentally retarded students. The analysis in this study was carried out within five stages, namely: (1) data reduction, (2) data display, (3) conclusion drawing, (4) results validity enhancement and (5) narrative analysis results. The results of this research show that physical education can be a medium for mentally retarded students' personal development, which includes some aspects of them, such as; physical education is proven to enhance the students' concentrations and focuses, increase their self-confidences and physical activities can help students to interact socially well and improve their self-developments.

Keywords: physical education, mentally retarded, self-developments

¹ Correspondence: email bramryd@gmail.com

1. Introduction

Education plays an important role to form the personality, character and self-development in order to achieve the life of the nation. With self-development within every child in a country, the education in the future is expected to be better for the nation and the state. As the subject of the implementation of education, all citizens are given the opportunity to utilize the broadest level, as expected. Education here includes education for normal children and the education of children with disabilities. For the normal children are provided with public schools, and for children with disabilities are provided with special schools for children with special needs. Educational institutions that provide educational services for children with special needs are Extraordinary School (SLB). Keep in mind that children with special needs are also children of our country that can grow and develop into adults who have high self-confidence and self-esteem in leading and devoting themselves for the nation in the future.

In fostering and developing education for children with special needs require attention of various parties concerned, for children with special needs, especially mentally retarded children, urgently need real care and guidance to improve their potential and capabilities. According Armatas, V (2009) in the Journal of Sports and Health Research suggests that "*Mental retardation (MR) is a genetic disorder in manifested significantly below average overall intellectual functioning and deficits in adaptive behavior. Mental retardation is a particular state of functioning that begins in childhood and is characterized by decreased intelligence and adaptive skills and is the most common developmental disorder*"(Bregman, 1991).

Sari & Altıparmak, 2008; Karakaya, (2005) in the International Journal of Science Culture and Sport states that "*Mental Retardation (MR) (also called intellectual disabilities or cognitive disabilities) is one of the most common disability types seen in the society*" (Gulsen Filazoğlu-Çokluk, et all, 2015: 57). MR Mental retardation or intellectual disability or also called cognitive disabilities are one of the most common types of disability in society.

This means that mental retardation is inherited genes that significantly strike intellectual functioning and adaptive behavior. Besides, mental retardation is a particular state of a function that begins from early childhood and is characterized by the reduction of intelligence and adaptive skills which are considered as the most common developmental disorder. The life process of mentally retarded children with their low power limitations of thinking and resistance in their personalities led to a negative impact in their daily lives.

Self-development is one of the important aspects of the person's personality. Self-development is a form of manifestation of self-actualization, which is a process to

manifest the best of him/herself, in line with his/her potential and ability. Every individual has the power that comes from him/her, but many people do not have the ability to feel anything, feeling useless and unable to achieve self-actualization. The development of one's self is the most valuable attribute of a person in social life. Because with the self-development, one is able to actualize all her/his potential. Self-development is required both by the children and parents, individually or in groups.

In the world of education, sport is part of an educational system that promotes physical activity for a healthy life in everyday life. Sports in school which is known as *Penjasorkes* (Physical Education, Sport and Health) also has an important role in the formation and development of basic motor skills instill the values, attitudes and healthy living habit. Physical education for children with special needs typically is associated with adaptive physical education. Fundamentally, adaptive physical education is the same as the regular physical education. Physical education is one aspect of the whole processes of education as a whole.

Physical education for children with intellectual challenges often has obstacles in self-adjustment which can be caused by a weak physical state, easily tired. Therefore, it is very necessary for physical education to maintain and improve their health as well as in the sports element of the game which can create cooperation, thus directly or indirectly, education and sport can be useful as a means of personal development among children with intellectual challenges.

Physical education for children with intellectual challenges is a media to assist them in developing themselves, at least they can establish themselves. Physical education for individuals with special needs has the objective to improve the growth and physical development, motor skills and intellectual. The process of education is important to instill the values of positive attitudes towards the limited ability both physically and mentally, so that they can socialize with the environment and have self-confidence and self-esteem.

Situations and circumstances like these that are prompted the authors to examine students interested in a Special School Multiple Disabilities Bina Sejahtera in Surakarta. Along with physical education, activities are also considered to help the self-development in children with intellectual challenges, and able to help the children for being concentrated and focus on what will be done in the future.

2. Research Method

The method used in this research is descriptive qualitative case study approach. The study takes place over three stages. The first phase is the collection of data that was to collect data on the location of the study by observation, in-depth interview, and

documentation. The second stage is data implementation analysis. The early implementation of the initial data analysis, verification, enrichment and deepening of the data and developed in the form of data presentation and followed by formulating the final conclusions. The third stage is the preparation of the study report, in this stage the validity of research reports is tested and discusses the reports that has been compiled with some experts then revise the report, and compiled a final report of the study.

This study will be conducted in Special Schools Multiple Disabilities Bina Sejahtera Surakarta. This school has male and female students who have multiple disabilities which are dominated by students with mental retardation. The sampling technique used was purposive sampling and snowball sampling. Sources of data in this study include students with intellectual challenges, physical education teachers, homeroom, and parents.

Data collection techniques used includes techniques of observation, interviews, literature review, and documentation. Meanwhile, in order to establish the validity of the data, it was used inspection technique with four criteria: the degree of confidence (credibility), transferability, dependability, and certainty. The data analyzed qualitatively were derived from data obtained from various sources; they were interviews and field notes. Data analysis phase performed in this study namely: (1) data reduction, (2) data, (3) conclusion, (4) enhancement the validity of the results, and (5) narrative analysis results.

3. Result and Discussion

This study used a system of interviews and observations got from the field, the object under study was retarded children who had an average age of 9-15 years. In the early stages of research in November 2016, initial observation on the subject that had been determined, observing mentally retarded children when they were in the classroom, outside the classroom, in sports and when they were playing. In this chapter, the researchers will present the result that had been obtained from interviews with informants through direct observation (passive participant), the researcher could analyze about children with intellectual challenges while doing sports and analyze whether physical education can be a means of self-development in mentally retarded students. By the interviews with the informants, the researcher could analyze the things that come up and expressed by informants with descriptive procedures include written or oral form based on the observed behavior of people or about how a result of analysis of data obtained by in-depth interview, observation and also reading the related research diktat experienced as follows:

3.1 The phenomenon exhibited by children with intellectual challenges in daily activities

Children with mental retardation have the disturbance in the function of the intellectual and social adaptations that occur during their development. The lack of special assistance and attention in the school-age children resulting in children with mental retardation are not able to develop properly. Usually the children have always failed to do in their daily tasks independently without the assistance. Always make mistakes due to their carelessness when doing something, it because they do not understand whether thing is right or wrong. They are often difficult to maintain concentration of attention during playing or doing activity. They also do not seem listen to people who speak to them and most likely to forget the everyday activities. While the adaptive behavior of children with intellectual challenges still need special assistance during the move both within the school and the community, because children with intellectual challenges still able to lead and take care of themselves. The Interaction of children with intellectual challenges in the society is still difficult to interact with their peers; they tend to associate with normal children under age. In any school environment, children with intellectual challenges are difficult to adjust, hard to understand the norms, and even they are difficult to control themselves and prone to bullying.

There seems to be common perception even though the teachers teach in different classes and dealing with children who have mental retardation and the same behavioral properties. Mentally disabled is a serious disruption in the power of thought and adaptive behavior. This is because children have difficulty in thinking and uncontrolled adaptive behavior, so they easily disrupt their friends.

Based on the findings above it can be concluded that the phenomenon exhibited by children with intellectual challenges in everyday life such as: difficult to control himself, his behavior is out of control, difficult to concentrate, sometimes disturb their peers, silent and introvert, tend not understand what goals they behave, many perform movements that are not controlled, tend to seek out the attention of others, while talking like upside down, need help from others to do the activity, lost in his own world, tend to be shy and lacking in confidence, less focus towards something.

3.2 The motion behaviors of mentally retarded students when they are in out and inside the physical education activities

The learning process of physical education is designed to improve physical fitness, develop motor skills, knowledge, health behavior, active cooperation, and emotional intelligence. Follow the physical education experience for students will help them understand how to perform the movement safely, efficiently, and effectively. Physical education itself is not only given to public schools only, but will also be given to

children with special needs school and children with intellectual challenges are no exception.

Every child who needs more like mental retardation have the ability to move differently, it depends on the strength and condition of the body, one of the disadvantages that children with intellectual challenges has in doing physical education activities is the motor skills. In importance to improve the motor skills of children with intellectual challenges, to be sure the child should always perform motor activity regularly to get accustomed to the movement. Factors that occur in children with intellectual challenges are in need of activities related to their physical health, for example, with exercises that can improve motor skills through basic movements for children with intellectual challenges.

Based on the findings above it can be concluded that the behavior of motion of children with intellectual challenges out and inside activities of physical education is experiencing difficulty in performing activities of physical education, unperfected movement, they need the help and guidance of teachers, very enthusiastic and follow the spirit physical education activities, and conduct more controlled motion when doing physical education activities.

3.3 The ability of children with intellectual challenges following the physical education activities and any constraints faced by these children

Retarded children always show the unique behavior and characteristics. Some of them are still silent and hung themselves; some are difficult to control themselves by showing excessive behavior and children with intellectual challenges are still weak in the power of thinking, so they are difficult to concentrate and focus. To set the adaptive behavior and their concentration power, retarded children should get plenty of exercise. Researchers found that the special proper guidance enables mentally disabled children to control themselves and be more concentrate.

“Aktivitas jasmani tidak hanya baik untuk mengencangkan otot. Hal ini dapat membantu menjaga konsentrasi anak. Ketikan anak-anak melakukan aktivitas jasmani dan olahraga, otak mereka melepaskan zat kimia yang disebut neurotransmitter. Neurotransmitter termasuk dopamin, yang terlibat dengan perhatian. Untuk menilai perilaku adaptif anak-anak tunagrahita saat berolahraga dan cara memberi perlakuan yang tepat, terlebih dahulu kenali arah minat anak tersebut dalam berolahraga. Jika anak menutup diri dan diam saat di lapangan, hal ini bisa menjadi suatu gambaran yang di tunjukkan oleh anak. Dengan memberi kesempatan untuk melakukan aktivitas jasmani membuat anak tersebut melepaskan diri dan mencoba sesuatu hal yang baru dengan banyak beraktivitas menggerakkan tubuhnya. Sedangkan bagi anak tunagrahita yang

tingkah lakunya sulit dikontrol, mereka bisa di arahkan ke dalam tugas ajar yang membuatnya bisa melakukan gerakan dengan baik dan mengurangi kecenderungan sulit untuk dikontrol. Dan juga bisa melatih konsentrasi serta fokus pada anak tunagrahita melalui tugas ajar yang anak-anak tunagrahita lakukan."

Physical activity is not only good for toning muscles, but also can help to keep a child's attention. While children doing physical activity and exercise, their brain releases chemicals called neurotransmitters. Neurotransmitters is kind of dopamine, which is involved with attention. To assess adaptive behavior retarded children during exercise and how to give the right treatment, the teacher must first identify the direction of the child's interest in sports. If the child becomes introvert and quiet while in the field, it could be a sign which are showed by the children. By giving the opportunity to do physical activity makes the child to break away and try something new with a lot of activities to move his/her body. As for retarded children whose behavior is difficult to control, they can be guided to the tasks that can make them doing the better movements and reduce the tendency to be hard to control and also can train their concentration and focus.

Therefore, we can provide enough activity space for children to train the adaptive power of thought and behavior, such as taking children to do physical activities outside of teaching learning and also directed them to be able to mingle with the people, and can direct where the behavior that endeared the retarded children then it is easier to give proper treatment to develop themselves through physical activity and sport.

Based on the findings above it can be concluded that the retarded children' ability to follow the physical education activities are different, some of them are good enough to carry out the task of teaching from teachers, some are afraid, but are excited to do physical education activities. While the obstacles faced by children with intellectual challenges in conducting physical education activities is the weak cognitive and adaptive behavior that resulted in the grasp of those responses are not well coordinated, takes a long time to accept the teacher's explanations, behavior that is difficult to control, difficult children to concentrate and lack of focus, and pessimism that sometimes arise in children with intellectual challenges.

3.4 How teachers give treatment in children with intellectual challenges while doing sports activities in physical education

It is known that children with intellectual challenges have limited power capability, so many problems arise. The problems they face are relatively different. However, there are also some problems being experienced by a group of them. Not infrequently, the

parents and teachers of children's mental retardation was not noticed or heard what they said. It often happens that mentally disabled children hear what is said and ordered just that they do not understand and demonstrate an attitude that does not care and did not hear what was said.

Mentally retarded children are also known to have problems with memory or short term memory, and difficult to follow instructions or orders as well as a concern that is easily changed. With conditions as above, the role of the teacher is highly demanded to be able to play an active role in mentoring specifically to direct the behavior of children with intellectual challenges properly and appropriately. Particularly for physical education teachers during physical education teaching, teachers are required to be able to direct the child in physical activities with the problems that exist in children with intellectual challenges that have low power level capabilities.

As the reality, many of mentally retarded children are need special assistance when they want to perform an activity. With teachers' attention and special treatment to mentally retarded children can add to the interest and enthusiasm of them to perform an activity with more concentration and self-control to get things done properly and appropriately.

Based on the findings above it can be concluded that the way teachers give treatment in children with intellectual challenges while doing sports activities in physical education include teachers use methods and their own way adapted to the conditions of children, provide treatment and handling in accordance with their needs, giving special treatment with assistance to every child, exemplifies the movements to be followed and carried the child, motivate and give more encouragement, to approach the emotional and individual, and many provide guidance and special attention to children.

3.5 Activities of physical education for personal development in students

Physical education and sport can help them to focus on the things that will be done and help maintain behavior patterns become more regular, physical exercise such as exercise can help cultivate gestures well and reduce the chance of emotions, it increases oxygen to the brain, which can help concentrate and behavior can be organized and calm. Doing regular physical activity can help them to train their capability and can be a means of self-development when it is done properly and correctly.

Activities of physical education for mentally retarded children' self-development are as a means of increasing confidence, increase courage in expressing opinions, improve social communication, cultivate an attitude of discipline and care, increasing independence, helping children with intellectual challenges cultivate body and set the

pattern of their movements so that they can concentrate well as well as children with intellectual challenges make life becomes more positive.

Broadly speaking, the researcher observed, interviewed informants and document the behavior of children with intellectual challenges as well as the search data related to physical education for the development of mentally retarded children, researchers summarizes all the results and that will be discussed at sub discussion. Researcher must first discuss their perception of the similarity of some of the informants as well as some of the results of the data that has been observed in the field, the activities and behavior of children have mental retardation average shows the attitude and behavior are almost the same. So the data and the results of the interview are inextricably linked to one another.

4. Discussion

4.1 Behavior shown by children with mental retardation in their daily life

The perception of children with mental retardation can be seen from their daily life. It is mostly shown when they are playing or doing sport activities in school, class, and home. Based on the research, children with mental retardation show same behavioral patterns. They are cognitive disorders which are marked with lack of attention and concentration and also social adaptive behavior which is inappropriate with their age.

Mental retardation is also known as mental sub-normality. James Payne & Patton (1981: 31) explain that, *"A state of incomplete mental development of such a kind and degree that the individual is incapable of adapting himself to the normal environment of his flow in such a way to maintain existence independently of supervision, control, or external support"*. Children with mental retardation are them who have obstacle or retardation of mental development that is accompanied by inability to learn and adapt.

The weaknesses that had by children with mental retardation make them have many problems in their daily life. The problems appear in the context of education and social life in family and society. This research found that children with mental retardation have same behavior in their activities. Based on observation done in school, most of them show poorly controlled behavior, difficulty concentrating, and sometimes they tend to annoy their friends. They incline to seek attention around them, hardly concentrate, annoy their friends inside or outside the class, overactive, don't understand about norm and value, have no purpose in doing something, and have less focus while they are in a communication. There is also child with mental retardation who has out of control behavior like showing excessive emotion which can spur their anger.

Adaptive behavior in children with mental retardation make them has not be able to take care of themselves in their daily life. Children with mental retardation often

show poorly controlled behavior, annoying body movement, and low concern with the environment around them. They build their own world that makes them hard to be controlled. Their behavior gives a negative impact in teaching and learning activity for them that can low their concentration and focus. They are indeed to do some task given by other people but, due to their weaknesses, they often cannot understand the purpose. Generally, they still cannot cope with themselves. They still need other people help to do their activities.

4.2 Motion behavior of children with mental retardation inside and outside sport activities

Sport is part of human life activities that become individual life need. While sport is given to children, the exercise activities should consider the needs and maximum response capabilities of children body. Not all children are born perfect. Some of them have physical and mental weaknesses.

Physical education given for children with mental retardation should be in lower percentage than normal children. Children with mental retardation can receive physical activities more than children with other disabilities. It is stated by The Office for Recreation and Sport (ORS, 2006) in Helen McLaren (2010: 12), from ABS General Social Survey (2007) data, that *“individuals with a disability were almost 50 per cent less likely to participate in sport or active recreation than individuals with no disability”* and *“those with an ‘intellectual’ or ‘psychological’ disability were least likely to participate in sport or active recreation compared to other types of disabilities”* (ORS, 2006).

Actually, physical education activities give many advantages for children with mental retardation. Talia Collier in International Journal of Physical Medicine & Rehabilitation conveys, *“Benefits of exercise and sport participation in children with disabilities include social integration, peer acceptance, cognitive development, achievement, social integration, and feelings of normalcy”* (2014: 3). According to Talia Collier, sport exercises and activities can give many advantages to children with disabilities that are connected to social integration, acceptance of people in the same age as friend, cognitive development, achievement, and their normal feelings.

Moreover, Niemann (2000) in Nevzat Demrci in International Conference on Education and Educational Psychology (ICEEPSY 2012) mendefinisikan bahwa *“the physical activities have positive influences and he shortly explained the uses of it on the child and teens like this: While it shortens stress, anxiety and depression, produces positive influence on autistic teens having learning disability and strongest the academic performance”* (2012: 1573). Neimann claims that physical activities give some positive impacts to for children and teenagers including; reduce stress in shorter level, reduce anxiety and depression, result

positive impact to the children or teenagers with autism who have learning disabilities related to academic performance.

Based on the data from ORS above, it is shown that individual with intellectual or psychological disabilities can more active participating in sports activities than they who have other disabilities. The result of the research shows that SLB CG Bina Sejahtera Kota Surakarta has given proper physical education. They provide sport activities that can maintain children's physical fitness, improve physical growth, build better psychological conditions, train and improve the basic motor skills, instill discipline and fairness, make children be autonomous and foster their confidence, and also improve their social interaction.

4.3 The ability of children with mental retardation in sport activities and the problems faced by them

Motion needs of children with mental retardation must be enormous since there is some obstacle experienced by them in response to environmental stimuli. It is given to make the motion, mimicking the motion and for them with physical disability, they cannot perform correct movement. This happens because children with mental retardation have problems in their sensor, motor development, learning, and behavior that could hamper their physical development.

Trudeau and Shephard (2008) in Nevzat Demrci through International Conference on Education and Educational Psychology (ICEEPSY 2012) states that "*It is pointed out that the physical activity has two positive influences on developing the children's learning functions. While the first one is an important argument to Increase the academic success, the second one is a kind of instrument to Decrease the irritable Behaviours derived from the education program.*" (2012: 1573). It is explained that physical activity has two positive influences on the children's learning function development. First, is an important argument for improving academic achievement and second is a kind of tool to reduce the irritable behavior that comes from education programs.

Although the children with mental retardation are able to perform physical education activities well, there are some obstacles that make them difficult to perform those movement activities. Those obstacles are related to their low power of thought so it makes their comprehension to the response and task given is not well coordinated. It causes some problems in performing motor activity in sports education

Shields and Synnot (2016) in BMC Pediatrics state that "*Children with disability growing niche to focus on personal factors, while parents focus on familial, social and policy and program factors*". It means that children with disabilities tend to focus on personal factors, while parents focus on family, social and policy and program. Therefore, it can

be concluded that the problems that make children with mental retardation experience difficulties in implementing activities are on themselves.

The approach given in children with mental retardation in CG SLB Bina Sejahtera Surakarta is usually done through individual approach although sometimes physical education is also done in groups. Disabilities had by children with mental retardation cannot be treated the same way for one to another because children with mental retardation have their own uniqueness. Therefore, in carrying out physical education activities, they still need guidance, direction, and even help to make them confident to perform physical education activities like other normal children.

4.4 How teachers give treatment to children with mental retardation while doing sports activities in physical education

The treatment given by physical education teachers can be done by give some example of movements to be followed and carried out by children including doing warm up, doing gymnastics and other physical activities. Giving examples and guiding children with mental retardation according to their needs is a proper way of handling the physical education activities. In addition, doing emotionally and individual approach will also make them feel valued and cared. Thus, children with mental retardation will have the motivation to do motion activities in physical education well.

Ahmed Shahin and Srividhya S in International Journal of Physical Education, Sports and Health states:

“Physical activity should be introduced in the form of Physical education curriculum right at the early school level where it would endow with opportunities to learn to understand both kinesthetically and cognitively movements within skills (quick/slow release the ball) and also the movement sequence or motor skill (throwing or kicking) within the game or activity context. The structured activities in the form of any games would have etiquette, strategies, tactics and rules, and provide new vistas to learn them would be part of this curriculum knowledge-based approach”

(2016: 310).

Children with mental retardation who tend to feel bored to something they dislike can cause a lack of attention to the teacher's command and direction. The teacher's instructions that are too fast or too long also make them do not understand about what is being described. Therefore, in carrying out physical education activities, they need direction, guidance, and assistance from the teachers. It is required a different method to teach physical education activities for them. The instructions should be done gradually and by giving an example. They must be often helped to perform the

movements as instructed by the teacher. The help done by teachers should be done carefully in order to avoid muscles injury or other injuries. To teach one movements, it often must be done repeatedly until the children understand well. If it has been understood, then it can be continued to other movements. There is a possibility of children with mental retardation that refuse to do sports activities. If it happens, they should not be forced but they should motivate and encourage children to join with other friends and work out together.

4.5 Physical education activities for students' personal development

Physical education also become one media to help self-development of children with mental. Many things can be acquired when they perform physical activity. By exercising, they will begin to understand the meaning of working together with his friend. In addition, while doing physical activity, they can physically feel the joy and excitement that can pump their motivation and enthusiasm in their daily lives.

Gülşen Filazoğlu-Çokluk through International Journal of Science Culture and Sport explains:

"Sports enable the individuals with disabilities to improve physically, psychologically and socially and facilitate their integration in the society (Savucu & Biçer, 2009). This positive effect on individuals with MR is emphasized in many researches (Carmeli et al 2004). Physical activities affect many variables positively such as self-concept, social adaptation (İlhan2007), attention level (Lois, Baron & Christine Faubert, 2005), hyperactivity and happiness level, motor behaviors and social abilities (Erdem 2005), communication skills (Krebs 2005), happiness levels (Damentko 2005) and perception growth (Çamlıyer 1995)"

(2015: 8).

Based on the above opinion, it can be concluded that sport activities can give a positive impact for children with mental retardation's self-development. With a wide range of activities undertaken in physical education, children with mental retardation is expected to be able to recognize their own personality, regulate their behavior patterns and can adjust themselves well in their daily life both at school and in society. Some self-development components that can be integrated into physical education include self-care, help themselves, communicate and socialize daily living skills, leisure time, self-confidence, self-reliance, and social interaction.

5. Conclusion

Based on the analysis of data from the previous discussion, it can be acquired some conclusions as follow:

- a) The phenomenon of behavior exhibited by children with intellectual challenges include hard to control themselves, their behavior are out of control, difficult to concentrate, sometimes disturb their peers, silent and introvert, tend not to understand what goals they behave, plenty of uncontrolled movements, tend to seek out the attention of others, produce unclear speaking, need help from others to do the activity, lost in his own world, tend to be shy and less confident, less focus towards something.
- b) Conduct motion retarded child when outside and inside the physical education activities that have difficulties in performing activities of physical education, movement indicated less than perfect, still need the help and guidance of teachers, very enthusiastic and follow the spirit of physical education activities, as well as the behavior of motion more controlled when doing physical education activities. Through physical activities such as activities of motion of physical education can be an alternative to help children with intellectual challenges to channel their motion behaviors that are sometimes not balanced and less coordinated.
- c) Ability retarded children follow the physical education activities with each other have differences, is good enough to carry out the task of teaching of teachers, some are afraid, but the spirit of doing physical education activities. While the obstacles faced by children with intellectual challenges in conducting physical education activities that weak cognitive and adaptive behavior that resulted in the grasp of those responses are not well coordinated, takes a long time to accept the teacher's explanations, behavior that is difficult to control, difficult children to concentrate and lack of focus, and pessimism that sometimes arise in children with intellectual challenges.
- d) How teachers give treatment in children with intellectual challenges while doing sports activities in physical education include teachers using its own methods and means adapted to the conditions of children, provide treatment and handling in accordance with their needs, giving special treatment to assistance to every child, exemplifies movements to be followed and carried the child, motivate and give more encouragement, to approach the emotional and individual, and many provide guidance and special attention to children.

- e) Activities of physical education for self-development in children “*tunagrahita*” namely as a means of increasing confidence, increase courage in expressing opinions, improve social communication, cultivate an attitude of discipline and care, increasing independence, helping children with intellectual challenges cultivate the body and regulate their movement patterns so as to concentrate well and make the child's life becomes more positive mental retardation. Physical education is one of the means to establish a self-development in children with intellectual challenges. By doing various positive activities in their daily life is very important for children with intellectual challenges in doing its own development that includes taking care of yourself, take care of yourself, help yourself, communication, socialization, life skills and leisure time environment of family, school and community.

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